

METHODOLOGY OF IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS IN THE SPHERE OF SPORTS ACTIVITIES BASED ON MASS SPORTS EVENTS

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Abstract. *This article examines the methodology of improving the professional training of students studying in the sphere of sports activities of higher educational institutions through mass sports events. The proposed approach is aimed at combining theoretical knowledge and practical skills, in the process students develop organizational, leadership and teamwork skills. Through sports activities, students develop the necessary skills for their future professional activities.*

Keywords: *professional training, mass sports events, sports management, organizational skills, higher education, physical education, practical training, sports activities, student training.*

Introduction. Today, the demand for qualified specialists in the sphere of physical education and sports is increasing. Physical education and sports specialists should not only have physical training, but also the skills necessary for organizing and managing mass sports events. Mass sports events allow students to test theoretical and practical knowledge, develop organizational skills. In developed foreign countries, as well as in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the competence approach is recognized in the training of modern, advanced and mature competent specialists, and the demand and need for its application is increasing. Also, in the preparation of future specialists, in order to ensure their competitiveness on a global scale and to develop into a staff capable of meeting modern requirements in every aspect, the use of various new and innovative methods and tools, their development and implementation is considered one of the urgent issues. Today, in our country, the development of physical education and sports, as well as mass sports, is recognized as one of the important directions of state policy. Special attention is paid to many such tasks. Also, after the pandemic situation in the country, with the initiatives of the honorable President, the measures and normative documents for the development of mass sports are established not only among the population, in remote areas, organizations and enterprises, but also in educational institutions, to develop, promote and hold systematically the road map of the events is defined. This article analyzes the methods aimed at improving the professional training of students through mass sports events.

Professional training of students is the process of formation of theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications of students in the chosen profession. This process ensures that the student acquires the skills and knowledge necessary to be successful in their future career.

Professional training includes the following main aspects:

- **Theoretical preparation.** Students acquire important knowledge in the chosen professional sphere. They can build their professional activities on the basis of this knowledge.

- **Practical skills:** Students develop their professional skills through practical training and experience during their studies. This is especially important in areas such as sports activities, as practical work is a key part of professional development.

- **Personal qualities and competencies:** Professional training of students is not limited to technical skills. They also develop organizational, leadership, teamwork, communication and management skills.

- **Innovative approaches:** updating and improving students' professional skills using modern technologies and methods. This may include, for example, digital tools or new pedagogical methods.

The professional training of students is based on the combination of their theoretical knowledge and practical skills, which prepares them for successful work in the future profession.

Mass sports events play a major role in improving the professional training of students in the sphere of sports activities in the higher education system. These activities are aimed not only at physical development of students, but also at teaching them organizational and management skills. During the training process, students' practical experience is increased by creating the opportunity to organize mass sports events. By hosting and participating in events, students develop not only coaching, but also management and leadership skills.

Methods

Theoretical preparation. Students are given in-depth knowledge of mass sports events by teaching them the theoretical aspects of sports activities. Subjects such as sports management, marketing and sports psychology are essential for the successful organization and management of sporting events. In theoretical training, students study the structure of sports events, their planning and implementation processes.

Practical training and experience. By participating in or organizing sports events, students improve their professional skills. In the process, students gain practical skills in teamwork, effective time management, and problem solving. During public events, students learn to solve many problems in practice, which gives them great professional experience.

Analysis and feedback. Analysis and feedback are important after every public sporting event. This process will be useful for students to evaluate their activities and organize future activities more effectively. Through suggestions and recommendations given by teachers and experts, students will have the opportunity to correct their shortcomings and improve their professional skills.

The influence of mass sports events on the educational process. The inclusion of mass sports events in the educational process plays an important role in the professional development of students. Students have the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in practice and test their knowledge and skills in real conditions. This will help them become qualified specialists in the sphere of sports. At the same time, students will have experience working closely with coaches, managers and other industry representatives.

There are a number of foreign methods for improving the professional training of students in the sphere of sports activities based on mass sports events. Their introduction in Uzbekistan will help to further improve the professional skills of students. Below are some foreign methods that can be adapted to local conditions:

1. **Service-Learning model.** Foreign experience: This model is widely used in many universities in the USA and Europe. Students learn not only theoretical knowledge, but also practice through community service. This method is effective for improving students' professional skills and developing their ability to solve real-world problems.

Implementation in Uzbekistan: Involve students in the sphere of sports in the organization of mass sports events and thereby create experience of public service. For example, universities can create opportunities for students to organize school sports events or team sports games. It will be a space for practical training and exchange of experiences for students.

2. Event-Based Learning. Foreign experience: in Europe and Australia, students at sports management faculties take an active part in the organization of major sports events. They gain experience in areas such as managing the entire event process, planning, financing and marketing.

Implementation in Uzbekistan: Universities in Uzbekistan can engage students in practical training to plan and organize mass sports events. It helps students develop the skills needed to plan events and run them successfully. For example, students should actively participate in the annual republican or regional sports festivals.

3. Mentoring (Coaching system). Foreign experience: In many developed countries, coaching programs are widely used in the sphere of sports. Students work with qualified professionals and experienced mentors, which gives them the opportunity for professional growth.

Implementation in Uzbekistan: Universities in Uzbekistan can establish a system to connect students with leading sports coaches and experts. This helps students gain professional guidance and experience working in the real world of sports.

4. Blended Learning. Foreign experience: "blended learning" method is widely used in the training of sports professionals in Great Britain and Canada. This method allows students to combine online and hands-on training. Theoretical knowledge is learned through online courses, while practical training takes place at real sports events or sports facilities.

Implementation in Uzbekistan: Establish online sports management and event planning courses for students in sports universities of Uzbekistan. Practical training can be carried out at mass sports events or in cooperation with local sports organizations.

5. Project-Based Learning. Foreign experience: developing practical knowledge and skills of students through projects is common in sports education in Germany and Scandinavian countries. Students design major sporting events and are responsible for all processes to make them successful.

Implementation in Uzbekistan: Sports students can be assigned the task of developing and implementing independent sports projects. For example, students may be tasked with creating a project for organizing sports competitions in schools or teams.

6. International Internship Programs. Foreign experience: Many universities around the world allow students to gain experience in other countries through international internship programs in sports management and sports activities. This allows students to learn new sports methods and expand their knowledge.

Implementation in Uzbekistan: Uzbek universities can establish cooperation with international sports organizations or foreign universities and create opportunities for students to participate in international practice programs. Through this process, students gain global experience in the sphere of sports and improve their skills.

Conclusion

Improving the professional training of students in the sphere of sports activities of higher education institutions on the basis of mass sports events will help them succeed in their future professional activities. These activities allow students to apply theoretical knowledge in practice, develop teamwork and organizational skills. At the same time, the integration of mass sports events

into the educational process serves as an effective way to improve the professional skills of students.

There are effective methods of improving the professional training of students in the sphere of sports activities through the use of mass sports events in foreign experience. By introducing these methods in Uzbekistan, it is possible to develop the system of sports education and expand the possibility of training qualified personnel in the sphere of sports.

1. **Enhancing Professional Training:** Mass sports events serve as a vital tool for enhancing students' professional training. They help students integrate theoretical knowledge with practice, acquire new skills, and develop teamwork abilities.

2. **Implementation of Innovative Methods:** The application of foreign experiences and innovative teaching methods, such as service learning, event-based learning, and blended learning approaches, creates further opportunities to improve students' professional training.

3. **Gaining Practical Experience:** Providing students with opportunities to participate in and organize real sports events enhances their experience and develops their professional skills.

4. **Community Relations:** Mass sports events strengthen students' connections with the community, which aids in their future success in the sports sphere.

Recommendations:

1. **Expanding Mass Sports Events:** It is essential to strengthen cooperation between universities and sports organizations in Uzbekistan to increase and improve the quality of mass sports events.

2. **Creating Mentorship Programs:** Establishing mentorship programs between students and experienced professionals will provide them with opportunities for professional growth and development.

3. **Expanding International Cooperation:** Strengthening cooperation with international sports organizations and universities to create opportunities for students to participate in international internships.

4. **Improving Monitoring and Evaluation Systems:** Developing effective monitoring and evaluation systems to assess the outcomes and impact of mass sports events.

5. **Conducting Training and Seminars:** Organizing training and seminars for students and educators by experts in sports education and management will help develop these processes.

These conclusions and recommendations play a crucial role in enhancing the professional training of students in the sphere of sports activities and assist them in pursuing successful careers in the sports sector.

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